

SIMILARITIES AND DISSIMILARITIES OF ACADEMIC AND GENERAL ENGLISH

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Annotation International cultural exchange has gradually increased as the process of economic globalization has continued to accelerate. English is now an essential part of our daily work and communication. College English teaching must reposition itself as education reform continues and English teaching quality improves. Academic English and general English have slightly different purposes. Academic English is based on professional needs, with a focus on developing students' professional learning abilities.

Key words Academic English, general English, economic globalization, essential part, communication, professional needs, learning abilities.

Introduction

To meet the needs of international construction in today's economic globalization and educational internationalization, colleges and universities must transform their traditional teaching goals and cultivate their academic abilities in English research. [1]

Hutchinson and Waters first introduced general English, which is divided into two categories: specific purpose English (ESP) and general purpose English (GPE) (GE). The specialized use of English is divided into two categories: English for Academic Purposes (EAP) and English for Occupational Purposes (EOP). From the standpoint of historical development, academic English has dominated ESP and continues to do so globally [2].

Learning English is an important part of higher education, which is in the process of English teaching, targeted for individual study, with the main goal of helping students to use flexible in the future work and professional direction, clear objectives and direction. As a result, it should prepare students to listen to lectures in English, take notes and read professional documents in English, write academic papers or articles in English, and participate in academic discussions in English. [3] Audio lingual Method (ALM) of the late 1940 and 1950s is considered as one of the best examples of periodical method. The ALM with its oral production drills is used almost half a century. Whereas, Direct Method started from behavioral theories of learning of the time. The approaches and techniques in the language teaching profession have stressed the importance of self – esteem, motivation, students cooperatively learning together, developing individual strategies for constructing meaning focused on the communicative process in language learning.

It is clear that, the methods which were devised 40 or 50 years ago or so, are too constructive to apply to a wide range of learners in an enormous number of situational contexts. There is no quick and easy method that provides success. It is essential to analyze the difference between approach and method.

Critics of audiolingual methodology were advocating more attention to rules and to the « cognitive code » of language. While in approach, teachers can choose particular designs and techniques for teaching a foreign language in a specific context.

Oral production drills can be a good example for audiolingual method that leads learners to improve their speech habits. However, in the communicative approach, it is important to create an Information gap between speakers. Thus, the need to communicate is authentic because communication must take place to narrow the gap and accomplish the task. The task can not be completed individually. Partners must work together to complete the assigned task successfully. The major

difference between academic and general English is in the functional purpose of language usage.

Academic English focuses on subject areas of study using specific words such as technical, medical, scientific etc. to help students obtain deeper insights in there discipline in the English language whereas General English aims to achieve a high standard of everyday English skills including reading, writing, speaking, and listening across common areas of communication. Moreover, academic English refers to formal English which teaches formal ways of speaking, writing such as those used in research papers. It can be argued that, in academic language one can face long and unfamiliar words, most of which have a specific or technical meaning. The most distinctive features of the two types of language can be observed in the register of the language used in a course book and a novel. The course book is considered as an academic genre, while the novel is a genre of general English. (Biber, Johansson, Leech, Conrad & Finegan, 1999)

Results.

The results show that, it is essential to classify similarities and dissimilarities of academic and general English from the perspective of a graduate student and an EAP teacher. Having a clear understanding of what academic English is like one can develop useful materials which will be helpful to learners. For instance, research articles, essays and lectures are the academic genres significant to EAP learners in understanding and creating academic contexts. The major difference between academic and general English is in the functional purpose of language usage.

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refers to formal English which teaches formal ways of speaking, writing such as those used in research papers.

Conclusion

It can be argued that, in academic language one can face long and unfamiliar words, most of which have a specific or technical meaning. The most distinctive features of the two types of language can be observed in the register of the language used in a course book and a novel. The course book is considered as an academic genre, while the novel is a genre of general English. (Biber, Johansson, Leech, Conrad & Finegan, 1999)

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